

Adsorption of Crystal Violet on Hydrrous Ferric Oxide. Part II

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The adsorption of Crystal violet by hydrrous ferric oxide increases with the increasing temperature. The heats of adsorption have been calculated from the adsorption isotherms for samples B and C at 30°, 35°, and 40°. The results show that the whole process of adsorption is endothermal; the heat of adsorption decreases with the increase of the dye adsorbed; the taking up of the dye by different samples of hydrrous oxide is a slow process, indicating the possibility for the existence of energy of activation; the adsorption is due to basic groups of the dye and may be said to be chemisorption.

The actual process of adsorption is exothermal and the total heat change observed is the algebraic sum of the heat of adsorption and the heat of dissociation of the dye micelle, which is endothermal.

The whole process of adsorption of the dye includes dissociation of aggregated micelle, followed by primary adsorption, and subsequent chemical union of the basic group with the acid group FeO_2^- , constituting the surface of the hydrrous oxide.

Hydrrous ferric oxide, being amphoteric in character, evokes acidic character when precipitated by an excess amount of alkali and adsorbs maximum amount of the basic dye, Crystal violet. In an earlier communication¹ it has been reported that the adsorption isotherms are sigmoid in nature. Isotherms of a similar nature are known in the case of gaseous adsorption on solid surfaces; Gyani² has reported similar adsorption isotherms for adsorption of various dyes by silica gel. That Freundlich's and Langmuir's equations are not applicable over the complete range of dye concentration has already been reported¹.

In the present communication the heats of adsorption of different samples have been calculated from the adsorption data for samples B and C at 30°, 35°, and 40°.

EXPERIMENTAL

The samples of hydrrous ferric oxide (A, B, and C) were precipitated by the addition of 10% excess, equivalent, and 10% deficient amounts of sodium hydroxide solution respectively to a known estimated volume of ferric chloride (E. Merck) solution at the room temperature (26°). These samples were washed with distilled water by decantation till the supernatant liquid was found free of chloride content. Sample C could not, however, be washed completely free of Cl^- ions due to increased peptisation on washing. The experimental details for the study of adsorption of Crystal violet dye by hydrrous ferric oxide at various temperatures have been described in the first part¹ of the paper.

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1. Hajela and Ghosh, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 781.

2. *Ind. & News Ed., J.I.C.S.*, 1950, 13, 1.

DISCUSSION

The adsorption isotherms for Crystal violet by samples B and C of hydrous ferric oxide (Figs. 1 & 2) show that the amount of dye adsorbed in g. mol./g. mol. of hydrous oxide increases with the increase of temperature though the effect is not very marked for dilute solutions of the dye. In the case of sample A, the effect of temperature changing between 30° and 35° and to 40° is not very marked. The complete equilibrium is attained in a smaller time of contact at higher temperatures. The convex nature of the curve indicates that the heat of adsorption of the dye is smaller than the heat of aggregation of the colloidal micelle of the dye and that the adsorption is endothermal. Similar results have been observed by Hajela and Ghosh³ in the case of Crystal violet adsorption by hydrous chromic oxide.

FIG. 1. Adsorption isotherm of Crystal violet on hydrous ferric oxide sample B at 30° & 35°.

FIG. 2. Adsorption isotherm of Crystal violet on hydrous ferric oxide sample C at 30° & 40°.

The values of heat of adsorption for samples B and C have been calculated from the equation:

$$\frac{RT_1 T_2}{T_1 - T_2} \ln \frac{C_1}{C_2} = Q$$

where C_1 and C_2 are the concentrations for the same amount of the dye adsorbed at temperatures T_1 and T_2 . The values of C_1 and C_2 are extrapolated from adsorption isotherms (Figs. 1 and 2) at 30°, 35° and 40° for the same amount of dye adsorption and are shown in Table I. The heats of adsorption (Q), as calculated from C_1 and C_2 data, are also shown in the table for samples B and C.

TABLE I

$X/M \times 10^4$	$C_1 \times 10^7$ at 30°	$C_2 \times 10^7$ at 35°	$C_2 \times 10^7$ at 40°	Q (calc.)
		Sample B.		
2.0	72.50	59.50		-7328.0
2.5	94.75	71.70		-10309.1
		Sample C.		
0.4	40.75		28.00	-14372
0.8	68.00		56.25	-7270
1.0	87.25		74.50	-6043

It may be noted from the table that the heat of adsorption for Crystal violet adsorption on hydrous ferric oxide is endothermic. The calculated heat of adsorption is, however, large. Similar results have been found in the case of Crystal violet adsorption by hydrous chromium oxide⁴. It seems that the adsorption is chemical in nature. It may be pointed out that Crystal violet dye in solution behaves as a colloidal electrolyte and on dilution, its micelle dissociates to simpler cations so that we have the equilibrium:

It is likely that the adsorption of simpler cations may be more prominent than that of the aggregated cations. During the process of adsorption, the simpler cations may be adsorbed readily and the above equilibrium is shifted so that more of the aggregated micelles dissociate into simpler cations. Thus, the total heat of adsorption calculated includes the heat of dissociation of the aggregated micelle. Ordinarily, in the adsorption process, the surface free-energy and entropy decrease so that from the equation:

$$\Delta F = \Delta H - T\Delta S$$

the adsorption process is always exothermic. In the present case, the adsorption of Crystal violet is linked with the dissociation of the aggregated micelle into simpler cations and the chemisorption of crystal violet by hydrous ferric oxide is preceded by physical adsorption.

It may be seen from the graph plotted between the amount of the dye adsorbed per g. mole of hydroxide and heat of adsorption for sample C (Fig. 3), that the heat of adsorption decreases with the increase of dye adsorbed.

FIG. 3 The graph between heat of adsorption and amount of crystal violet adsorbed by hydrous ferric oxide sample C.

on the hydrous oxide so that its surface assumes positive charge. It is probable that further uptake of cations would be opposed by the positively charged surface formed by the prior adsorption of the dye.

The taking up of the dye by the three samples of hydrous oxide is a slow process and indicates the possibility of the existence of energy of activation. The energy of activation could not, however, be calculated for want of sufficient data for the rate of adsorption at different temperatures. The slow rate for attaining equilibrium for the adsorption of Crystal violet by sample A points out that there is some heat of activation for this sample. Undoubtedly, the sample A is of acidic character, exerting greater influence on the chemisorption of the dye.

From the results presented in this series of papers, it may be concluded that the taking up of the dye by the hydrous ferric oxide is due to chemisorption, specially for sample A. The adsorption isotherms for any of the samples of hydrous oxide do not suggest the formation of any definite compound with the dye. Ackerman⁸, Biltz⁹, and Weiser¹⁰ also reported similar views in the case of Alizarin lakes and Congo-red lakes with several hydrous oxides.

5. *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1950, **8**, 314.

6. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 837.

7. 'Chemisorption', B. S. Publication, 1955, p. 155.

8. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 780.

9. *Ber.*, 1906, **38**, 4143.

10. "Inorganic Colloid Chemistry", 1935, Vol. II, p. 128.

Similar results have been reported by Beck *et al.*⁵ in the case of ethylene on tantalum and also by Bull *et al.*⁶ and Trapnel⁷. Hajela and Ghosh⁴ have also reported similar results in the case of Crystal violet adsorption by hydrous chromium oxide. The fall in heat of adsorption with the increase in the amount of adsorption may be attributed to the surface heterogeneity and the increasing repulsion between the surface and the adsorbate ions. On a heterogeneous surface, the active spots are statistically distributed for adsorption and the adsorption on most active sites would proceed rapidly. Even if a random coverage takes place initially, there will be subsequent spreading over the most active spots. Thus as the adsorption increases, the sites of smaller activity will be gradually covered for which heat of adsorption may continuously decrease. It is also noted that the adsorption of cations from Crystal violet have a peptising action

Hydrous ferric oxide is amphoteric in character¹¹, which can be shown by the following equations:

Equations (2) and (3) indicate the acid character and (1) and (4) indicate the basic nature.

It is possible that FeO_2^- on the surface of hydrous ferric oxide initiates the chemisorption of the coloured cation of Crystal violet, as has been suggested in the case of hydrous chromium oxide¹². It is possible that the adsorption takes place with the tertiary basic group in the dye cation and the active acid groups present in the hydrous oxide.

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11. Ghosh *et al.*, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1948, 17A, 93; *Kolloid Z.*, 1954, 135, 143; 1953, 132, 141; *Z. physical, Chem.*, 1955, 205, 160.
12. Hajela and Ghosh, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1959, 28A, 130.